

Using long-term condition monitoring data with non-Gaussian noise for online diagnostics

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Abstract

The number of timely diagnoses based on condition monitoring data is increasing with the growing usage of monitoring systems. In most of the methods used in these systems, a pre-established fault detection threshold is needed, while there are no specific limit values or thresholds in many cases, especially when the machine is unique. Also, in most actual applications, due to the kind of process and harsh environment, the noise inherent in the observed process exhibits non-Gaussian characteristics, making it a challenging task for diagnostics based on condition monitoring (CM) data. Therefore, this paper introduced a robust methodology based on the switching maximum correntropy Kalman filter (SMCKF) to address the mentioned problems (threshold and online diagnostics in the presence of non-Gaussian noise by using CM data). This approach uses multiple dynamic system models to explain different degradation stages, utilizing robust Bayesian estimation. As this approach is based on dynamic behavior, a threshold for diagnostics is no longer needed. Ultimately, the proposed approach is applied to the online diagnosis of simulated and actual data sets. The results of both simulated and real data sets prove the method's efficacy.

Keywords: diagnostics, condition monitoring, fault detection, Kalman filter, robust methods, non-Gaussian noise, dynamic linear model.

1. Introduction

Condition-based maintenance (CBM) has become increasingly popular in the industry with the development of condition monitoring systems. CBM software is developed to assess the machine's condition by collecting massive amounts of data during the operation of machines. Using long-term condition monitoring data is crucial in diagnostics and prognostics. Many methods published in recent years for CBM can be categorized into four main groups [1]: stochastic-based [2–4], machine learning-based [5–7], physics model-based [8, 9], and hybrid methods [10, 11]. Machine learning approach such as neural networks [12–19], have strong potential to be used for diagnostics and prognostics areas. Nevertheless, they need a large number of data for the model to be trained. Furthermore, by changing the domain of working or changing the machine, they need to retrain again, which is often not possible in actual application. On the other hand, physics model-based methods use a mathematical representation of the degradation process based on the failure mechanisms or the damage principle [1], which needs less training data. However, for some complex mechanical systems, it is hard to understand the physics of damage, which significantly restricts the range of

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application of mechanism modeling-based approaches. Compared to the previous methods, stochastic-based approaches (also named empirical model-based approaches) do not need a large number of degradation data and mechanical knowledge of equipment (physics or mechanical principles). Statistical model-based approaches work according to establishing statistical models based on empirical knowledge and generally try to model a degradation process using stochastic process models under a probabilistic method. Also, the stochastic-based model has an enormous potential to consider degradation uncertainty. Most of the mentioned methods work based on a pre-established fault detection threshold that is often provided by the manufacturer; a threshold corresponding to a change from "Good Condition" (healthy stage) to "Warning" (degradation stage) and from "Warning" to "Alarm" stage (critical stage). Unfortunately, we do not know about limit values or the desired lifetime in many cases, especially when the machine is unique. Also, it should be noted that most of these thresholds are introduced by manufacturing industries, and they are defined based on particular working and environmental conditions standards that may not be valid when the conditions change. In addition, this task will be more complicated when the machine works in a harsh area, where the inherent noise exhibit non-Gaussian characteristics. This may occur for several reasons. Wind inflows are one of the possible sources of impulsive noise in wind turbine [20–22], the falling ore on devices in the mining environment is another source that can be mentioned [23, 24].

The Kalman filter (KF) is a well-known, powerful tool in engineering applications such as diagnostics [25–29] and prognostics [30–33]. However, the KF gives the optimal solution when the process and measurement noise have a Gaussian distribution, whereas if noise has a different distribution, KF produces a sub-optimal solution. It is because only the second-order measurement information is used. Many methods have been developed to handle this drawback of the KF. For example, some researchers tried to develop filters for the system by considering its random impulsive behavior producing outliers in the data. In this family of methods, noise distribution is assumed to have non-Gaussian characteristics, which is fulfilled for distributions such as Student's t-distribution, stable distributions, etc. [34, 35]. However, finding analytic solutions for these distributions is complicated and needs high computational effort. Therefore, using them in practical applications is more complicated than using KF. Another approach that tries to handle non-Gaussian noise is its approximation with a Gaussian mixture distribution [36–39]. The high computational cost is the main drawback of these approaches. The third family of methods that tries to handle non-Gaussian noise is sequential Monte Carlo (SMC) sampling, which has the potential to approximate any distribution [40]. Particle filter (PF) is the most famous example [37, 41]. The unscented Kalman filter (UKF) is similar to the PF but uses different sampling techniques [42]. As with the previous methods, the computational cost is the biggest drawback of this approach. To reduce the aforementioned disadvantages, Izanloo et al. [43] presented the correntropy filter (C-Filter) for state estimation and indicated that the C-Filter has better performance than KF in the presence of non-Gaussian noise, thanks to using correntropy criterion, which utilizes higher-order measurement signal information. Also, a new version of KF based maximum correntropy criterion was developed [43–46], which is robust in the presence of noise with non-Gaussian characteristics.

However, the most significant limitation of KF and maximum correntropy criterion Kalman filter (MCKF) used for diagnostics and prognostics is that the degradation process must be time-invariant. However, in practical application, the degradation process is composed of several components that change over time, see Section 2.1. Therefore, using a single model to describe the whole process would make incorrect state estimations and cause divergence or fluctuation. In lieu of this, the switching Kalman filter (SKF) is proposed to handle the mentioned issue when the dynamic behavior of a process changes during the time and, if not possible, to use an unique model. The SKF is frequently employed to track multiple moving targets [47], econometric time series [48] and meteorologic observations [49]. Likewise the SKF is used in maintenance areas; for instance, to detect sensor and actuator faults [50]. In [51], SKF is employed to find changing points in nonlinear stochastic systems. In [33, 52] SKF is used to diagnostics and prognosis of bearing. However, most of these methods assumed the noise distribution is Gaussian. The use of standard SKF for online condition monitoring in most actual applications in the presence of non-Gaussian noise may be problematic. Furthermore, our previous work [53] focused on identifying and analyzing the degradation process using the real benchmark data sets (available in the prognostics area), which confirms the hypothesis of noise with non-Gaussian characteristics even in the laboratory data sets. To address the above problems, this

paper introduced a novel, robust approach for online diagnostics without using a threshold in the presence of impulsive noise based on SKF and MCKF. The proposed method improves the accuracy and effectiveness of online diagnostics based on SKF, particularly in harsh environments, when the noise inherent in the observed process exhibits non-Gaussian characteristics. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- A model of health index (HI) data was proposed as three segments sequence with non-Gaussian noise (Student's t-distributed) to describe the degradation process, which can be used to simulate the artificial data set.
- Switching maximum correntropy Kalman filter regime is derived, which is a robust version of SKF in the presence of noise with non-Gaussian characteristics.
- An online diagnostics method based on SMCKF is proposed, and extensive experiments are carried out on the simulated data set in the presence of Gaussian and non-Gaussian noise and FEMTO and wind turbine datasets to verify its effectiveness.

The paper is structured as follows: after the introduction, in Section 2, the critical aspects of the processing methods are described in theory. Then, in Section 3, the results for simulated data are presented. Finally, the results of applying the proposed approach to two benchmark data sets are presented in Section 4 with an indication of all intermediate steps. Conclusions are formed in Section 5.

2. Methodology

The data is acquired using sensors and goes to the SCADA system. After preprocessing in the SCADA system, the SCADA data is used as a HI for diagnostics and prognosis (SCADA data is usually a statistic or frequency domain feature of the sensor's data that is gathered in a specific duration of time). At the end, by using the SMCKF, the HI is segmented into three stages (healthy, degradation, and critical). More details about the algorithm are presented in the following subsections.

2.1. Long term data modeling

In the PHM community, one widespread assumption is to consider the HI value following specific trends during the degradation process. Therefore, based on the application, the researchers use several conventional models to describe the global trend of the degradation process, see Fig. 1. For instance, employing a linear trend is a common assumption to describe the drilling degradation process [1, 54], see panel (b) in Fig. 1. On the other hand, the exponential degradation is used to express the battery degradation process [55–58]. For the degradation process of other elements such as bearings, gears, and shafts, it is popular to use models [59, 60] like in (d), (e), (f) panels in Fig. 1. In this work, it is assumed that the degradation trend is divided into three stages (see panel (f) in Fig. 1). Considering some assumptions, some analogies between this model and the three steps of crack growth can be made. Continuous damage and fracture mechanics are investigated in detail using physics-based modeling, considering the dependence on the current stage [61]. Stage 1 considers there is no degradation; it can be compared to the healthy area or the initiation of a crack in the microscopic domain; the length of this stage is approximately unpredictable. Stage 2 represents linear degradation growth with the potential to compose different kinds of Gaussian and non-Gaussian noise plus fluctuations in deterministic trend (self-healing phenomena [54]); this step can be compared to the fatigue crack propagation. The length of this stage is varied. It depends on many parameters, such as load, temperature, etc. Stage 3 is a rapid exponential (or polynomial) degradation growth corresponding to a fast fracture area; see Fig. 2. The length of this stage is short. Such a model is frequently used in the literature [59, 60]. To bring this model closer to reality, a model based on the following assumptions is presented. In our previous paper [53], we demonstrate that the degradation process data are non-homogeneous (their characteristics change in time), may include some random components, and may exhibit non-Gaussian (heavy-tailed) behavior. The nature of the deterministic component and the scale of the data is different for different stages. However, a transition might exist for random components' distribution - from Gaussian to strongly non-Gaussian. In Fig. 3, we demonstrate the above characteristics and their correspondence with

the degradation process. Moreover, in Table 1, we show the main characteristics of the data corresponding to different stages that result from the preliminary analysis of the actual data also, for more details about the model, we refer to our previous work [53].

Figure 1: Different types of HI variations and degradation models: (a) good condition (constant trend), (b) good to gradual wear (linear trend), (c) exponential trend, (d) good to accelerated wear (linear trend), (e) good to accelerated wear (exponential trend), (f) three stages model (good, linear progress and exponential progress of degradation) [53].

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Multi stage degradation model, (a) three steps fatigue crack growth [62], (b) three stages degradation model [52].

Figure 3: The proposed long-term degradation model with three stages [53].

Table 1: Main characteristics of the data for three stages indicated in Fig. 3 [53].

	stage 1	stage 2	stage 3
Trend	constant	linear	exponential or polynomial
Scale	nearly constant	linearly growing	exp.or polynomial growing
Autodependence of the noise	white / colored	white / colored	white / colored
Distribution of the noise	Gaussian / non-Gaussian	Gaussian / non-Gaussian	Gaussian / non-Gaussian

2.2. Diagnostics

In this subsection, we focus on introducing the methodology for online diagnostics of the machines with long-term condition monitoring data.

2.2.1. Kalman filter

The KF is a kind of Bayesian filter used for recursive state estimation of a dynamic system by minimizing the mean squared error in the presence of process and measurement noise. The EKF works based on follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_t &= A_t x_{t-1} + q_t, \\ y_t &= H_t x_t + m_t, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where x_t is the actual state at time t and y_t is its observation, the matrix A_t describes the state-transition model, q_t is the process noise, H_t is the observation matrix, which maps the actual state space into the observed space, and m_t is the observation noise. The noise terms q_t and m_t are assumed to be normally distributed: $q_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, Q_t)$, $m_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, M_t)$. In the literature, several approaches can be employed to extract KF formulation: for instance, Bayesian rule, maximum posterior approaches (MAP), orthogonal principle, and weighted least square method (WLS). To describe the state estimation procedure given the observations y_t we need to introduce the notation of $\hat{x}_{t|t}$ and $\hat{x}_{t|t-1}$ being the posterior and the prior estimates of the state x_t given the observations till the time t and $t-1$, respectively. The cost function in WLS, defined as a sum of two squared quadratic norms [43], which combines the measurement (first term) and the prior estimate (second term) in finding the optimal posterior estimate of the x_t , is given as follows:

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \|y_t - H_t x_t\|_{M_t^{-1}}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \|x_t - A_t \hat{x}_{t-1|t-1}\|_{P_{t-1}^{-1}}^2, \quad (2)$$

where -1 in the superscript denotes matrix inversion, quadratic norm of a vector u defined with a weights matrix W is the quadratic form obtained with the formula (denoting matrix transposition with T in the

superscript):

$$\|u\|_W = \sqrt{u^T W u} \quad (3)$$

and $P_{t|t-1}$ is the prior estimate covariance matrix:

$$P_{t|t-1} = E[(x_t - \hat{x}_{t|t-1})(x_t - \hat{x}_{t|t-1})^T]. \quad (4)$$

The posterior estimate covariance matrix $P_{t|t}$ is expressed in an analogous way as above:

$$P_{t|t} = E[(x_t - \hat{x}_{t|t})(x_t - \hat{x}_{t|t})^T]. \quad (5)$$

The KF formulation can be derived by minimizing J from Eq. (2) with respect to x_t , namely the posterior estimator of the state of the model is defined as:

$$\hat{x}_{t|t} = \underset{x_t}{\operatorname{argmin}}\{J\}. \quad (6)$$

At the same time the covariance matrix is also estimated. The resulting recursive procedure is described with the following equations which are usually divided into two steps, namely the prediction step:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x}_{t|t-1} &= A_t \hat{x}_{t-1|t-1}, \\ \hat{P}_{t|t-1} &= A_t \hat{P}_{t-1|t-1} A_t^T + Q_t, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and the update step:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x}_{t|t} &= \hat{x}_{t|t-1} + K_t (y_t - H_t \hat{x}_{t|t-1}), \\ \hat{P}_{t|t} &= (I - K_t H_t) \hat{P}_{t|t-1} (I - K_t H_t)^T + K_t M_t K_t^T. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The term K_t in the above equations is called Kalman gain and for the standard KF its optimal value is given by the formula:

$$K_t = \hat{P}_{t|t-1} H_t^T (H_t \hat{P}_{t|t-1} H_t^T + M_t)^{-1}. \quad (9)$$

As we mentioned before, the KF gives the optimal solution when both the process noise and the measurement noise have a Gaussian distribution. For other distributions, the KF produces a sub-optimal solution, which is because only the second-order measurement information is used.

In the following subsection, the MCKF is derived to handle non-Gaussian noise based on the following references [43–46].

2.2.2. Maximum correntropy Kalman filter

In the following, for the model expressed with Eq. (1) another form of an objective function is introduced [43]. Based on the maximum correntropy criterion it has the form:

$$J_{MC} = G_\sigma(\|y_t - H_t x_t\|_{M_t^{-1}}) + G_\sigma(\|x_t - A_t \hat{x}_{t-1|t-1}\|_{P_{t|t-1}^{-1}}), \quad (10)$$

where $G_\sigma(u) = \exp(-\frac{u^2}{2\sigma^2})$ and σ is kernel size.

This function used instead of a previous cost function makes the estimation more robust in the presence of non-Gaussian noise, which is the case when the real observation process does not necessarily fulfill the assumptions of the KF model. The formulation of MCKF can be derived by finding x_t that maximizes the objective function J_{MC} given by Eq. (10). It should be emphasized that in the derivation based on WLS to obtain the solution given by a closed formula an approximation is made, namely the posterior estimate is replaced at one place with the prior estimate, i.e. $\hat{x}_{t|t} \approx \hat{x}_{t|t-1}$ (please see [43] for details). The resulting predict and update steps are driven by the same equations as for the standard KF, see Eq. (7) and (8) but the optimal Kalman gain for the MCKF is given with the formula:

$$K_t = \hat{P}_{t|t-1} \lambda_t H_t^T (H_t \hat{P}_{t|t-1} \lambda_t H_t^T + M_t)^{-1}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$\lambda_t = G_\sigma \left(\|y_t - H_t \hat{x}_{t|t-1}\|_{M_t^{-1}} \right). \quad (12)$$

In the state estimation procedure using MCKF, when a significant outlier appears, the term $y_t - H_t \hat{x}_{t|t-1}$ in Eq. (8) (usually called innovation or pre-fit residual) diverges, but K_t controls the divergence of the estimator $\hat{x}_{t|t}$. Please see references [43–46] for more details about the procedure of driving equations and stability.

To illustrate the performance of MCKF we consider a two-state dynamic system as follows:

$$x_t = A_t x_{t-1} + q_t, \quad y_t = H_t x_t + m_t + w_t, \quad A_t = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad H_t = [1 \ 0], \quad (13)$$

where Δt is the discretisation step size and for this case we consider $\Delta t = 0.1$. The initial parameters of estimator are $\hat{x}_{0|0} = [0 \ 0]^T$, $\hat{P}_{0|0} = [6.2e-08 \ 1.2e-06; 1.2e-06 \ 2.5e-05]$. The noise terms q_t and m_t are normally distributed: $q_t \sim \mathcal{N}([0; 0], [\frac{1}{4}(\Delta t)^4, \frac{1}{2}(\Delta t)^3; \frac{1}{2}(\Delta t)^3, (\Delta t)^2])$, $m_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 10)$. The additional term w_t is a non-Gaussian noise generated as a series of independent random variables from Student's t-distribution with number of degrees of freedom $\nu = 2.8$ (please note that this term is not included in the standard KF model).

The simulation results are plotted in Fig. 4. Panel (a) is presented an actual state by a red line, and the observation of the real state includes heavy-tailed noise. As we can see on panel (b) of Fig. 4, in the presence of impulsive noise, MCKF could properly track the mean state, while standard KF estimation was affected by heavy-tailed distributed noise and therefore could not follow the mean state with comparable accuracy.

Figure 4: State estimation in the presence of non-Gaussian noise, (a) measurement signal and real state, (b) results of state estimation with KF and MCKF.

2.2.3. Switching maximum correntropy Kalman filter

In this subsection, we introduce the switching maximum correntropy criterion Kalman filter, which is a robust version of SKF. The SMCKF can be described as a dynamic Bayesian network in which during the lifetime of the system we switch between different KF or MCKF models. see Fig. 5. The additional process

s_t called switching variable is introduced. Its state space is finite, i.e. consists of k values: $1, 2, \dots, k$. If $s_t = j$, the degradation process is in the j -th of k subsequent stages and the process x_t is in this stage modelled with the j -th of k MCKF models. In each time step both the switching model variable s_t and the state variable x_t are hidden and thus must be figured out from the observation y_t . This may cause numerical problems, especially when the number of the stages is increased, as argued in [63]. Kevin et al. in [43, 64], developed an approximation approach, namely the generalized pseudo-Bayesian (GPB) method, to solve this issue.

Figure 5: Dynamic Bayesian network.

Our goal in the segmentation through degradation stages is to evaluate, based on the measurement $y_{1:t} = \{y_1, \dots, y_t\}$, the probabilities of the model being in a specific stage at each time t which directly corresponds to the values of

$$\pi_t^j = P(s_t = j | y_{1:t}) \quad (14)$$

for $j = 1, \dots, k$. Note that the above probabilities are the ones filtered with the SMCKF based on measurement $y_{1:t}$. For modelling the process s_t we use a discrete time Markov chain, thus the non-filtered probabilities can be expressed with a recursive formula. Namely denoting the transition probabilities of s_t as $z_{ij} = P(s_t = j | s_{t-1} = i)$ (assumed to be time-invariant) we have:

$$P(s_t = j) = \sum_{i=1}^k P(s_{t-1} = i) \cdot z_{ij}. \quad (15)$$

The framework we use is similar to the one used in [43] and is based on the assumption that in general all parameters of the model, i.e. A_t , Q_t , H_t and M_t but also the form of state vector x_t , may explicitly depend on the current value of s_t . In contrary to [43] we assume that in each of 1 to k -th stages the current HI needs to be estimated using MCKF instead of KF. Thus, the Kalman gain is calculated using Eq. (11) which contains the coefficient λ_t . Likewise the covariance matrix of the innovation term $\epsilon_t = y_t - H_t \hat{x}_{t|t-1}$ (given the measurement till time t) contains the same coefficient λ_t , namely we obtain $\epsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, C_t)$, where C_t is given by the formula:

$$C_t = H_t \hat{P}_{t|t-1} \lambda_t H_t^T + M_t. \quad (16)$$

As we noted before, the parameters of the degradation model depend on s_t describing the current stage. The estimates $\hat{x}_{t|t}$ and $\hat{P}_{t|t}$ obtained by repeating iterations of SMCKF would be therefore different for each possible series of $\{s_1, \dots, s_t\}$. To reduce computational complexity of the algorithm (avoid iterating MCKF-s through all possible trajectories of s_t), we limit our procedure to iterate only through possible values of the switching variable in the current and previous time, i.e. s_t and s_{t-1} . Therefore we assume the following form of the conditional probability density function:

$$P(\epsilon_t = u | s_{t-1} = i, s_t = j, y_{1:t}) = g_{0, C_t}(u), \quad (17)$$

where $g_{\mu, \Sigma}(u)$ is multivariate Gaussian probability density function of the random variable with mean vector μ and covariance matrix Σ .

Using the Bayes' theorem conditioning on ϵ_t we obtain:

$$P(s_{t-1} = i, s_t = j | \epsilon_t, y_{1:t-1}) = \frac{g_{0, C_t}(\epsilon_t) \cdot P(s_{t-1} = i, s_t = j | y_{1:t-1})}{\sum_{l=1}^k \sum_{m=1}^k g_{0, C_t}(\epsilon_t) \cdot P(s_{t-1} = m, s_t = l | y_{1:t-1})}, \quad (18)$$

which holds for each pair of indices i and j . Summing these probabilities with respect to i (and using the definition of transition probabilities), we receive a recursive formula for the filtered probability of the j -th MCKF model:

$$\pi_t^j = P(s_t = j | \epsilon_t, y_{1:t-1}) = \sum_{i=1}^k P(s_{t-1} = i, s_t = j | \epsilon_t, y_{1:t-1}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k g_{0, C_t}(\epsilon_t) \cdot \pi_{t-1}^i \cdot z_{ij}}{\sum_{l=1}^k \sum_{m=1}^k g_{0, C_t}(\epsilon_t) \cdot \pi_{t-1}^l \cdot z_{lm}}. \quad (19)$$

We can apply this formula to calculate π_t^j -s in each step of the SMCKF.

To make the estimation procedure feasible at time iteration after prediction and update steps (described in the previous subsections) we add a approximation step which merges the estimates removing the dependence on previous values of the switching variable, thus we only need to store in the memory the estimates $\hat{x}_{t|t}$ and $\hat{P}_{t|t}$ for $k \times k$ pairs of possible values of s_{t-1} and s_t . For the estimates calculated given the specific realization of the switching variable process let us introduce the following notation: $\hat{x}_{t|t}|_{s_{t-1}=i, s_t=j}$ stands for the posterior estimate of x_t obtained for $s_{t-1} = i$ and $s_t = j$.

The approximated value of the posterior estimate $\hat{x}_{t|t}$ given s_t is evaluated taking a weighted mean of the state estimates obtained with each of the MCKS-s, i.e. starting with each of k possible values of s_{t-1} . Similar formula is applied to covariance matrices of the estimates. The two approximation formulas are following:

$$\tilde{x}_{t|t}|_{s_t=j} = \sum_{i=1}^k w_t^{ij} \hat{x}_{t|t}|_{s_{t-1}=i, s_t=j}, \quad (20)$$

$$\tilde{P}_{t|t}|_{s_t=j} = \sum_{i=1}^k w_t^{ij} (\hat{P}_{t|t}|_{s_{t-1}=i, s_t=j} + r r^T), \quad (21)$$

where $r = \tilde{x}_{t|t}|_{s_t=j} - \hat{x}_{t|t}|_{s_{t-1}=i, s_t=j}$. Using Bayes' theorem and applying the results of Eq. (18) and (19) we obtain the proper weights:

$$w_t^{ij} = P(s_{t-1} = i | s_t = j, \epsilon_t, y_{1:t-1}) = \frac{P(s_{t-1} = i, s_t = j | \epsilon_t, y_{1:t-1})}{P(s_t = j | \epsilon_t, y_{1:t-1})} = \frac{g_{0, C_t}(\epsilon_t) \cdot \pi_{t-1}^i \cdot z_{ij}}{\sum_{l=1}^k g_{0, C_t}(\epsilon_t) \cdot \pi_{t-1}^l \cdot z_{lj}}. \quad (22)$$

In this way k estimates, after multiplying to $k \times k$ posterior estimates in prediction-update steps, reduce back to k values in the approximation step. The approximated values of the state estimate and covariance matrix (which overwrite the posterior) are then used as an input to the prediction step (obtaining new priors) in the next time iteration of the SMCKF.

More theoretical details about the procedure of the switching structure (in the case of SKF which is analogous) and stability of the model are available in [64]. The SMCKF, which is composed of multiple MCKF-s with different state-space models, is applied to track changes in the degradation process. Then SMCKF is switched between the selected models according to their likelihood (Gaussian distribution of the innovation term) calculated from HI. Thanks to the use of the maximum correntropy criterion the procedure is more robust than in the case of SKF. It should be noted that for applying this approach, the degradation model should be selected based on the case's physics, as discussed in Section 2.1.

Based on our primary assumption, the degradation process comprises three stages. Three MCKF models are used to simulate healthy, degradation, and critical stage. According to [52, 65] the polynomial MCKFs of zero-, first-, and second-order are illustrated below, respectively. Using the superscripts to denote the

current value of the switching variable s_t we present the proposed models corresponding to each of the HI stages. The state vectors, model matrices, and covariance matrices of the model noise are as follows:

$$x_t^1 = \begin{bmatrix} x_t \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, x_t^2 = \begin{bmatrix} x_t \\ \dot{x}_t \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, x_t^3 = \begin{bmatrix} x_t \\ \dot{x}_t \\ \ddot{x}_t \end{bmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

$$A_t^1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, A_t^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, A_t^3 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \Delta t & \frac{(\Delta t)^2}{2} \\ 0 & 1 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (24)$$

$$Q_t^1 = \beta \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, Q_t^2 = \beta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(\Delta t)^3}{3} & \frac{(\Delta t)^2}{2} & 0 \\ \frac{(\Delta t)^2}{2} & \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, Q_t^3 = \beta \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(\Delta t)^5}{8} & \frac{(\Delta t)^4}{3} & \frac{(\Delta t)^3}{2} \\ \frac{(\Delta t)^4}{3} & \frac{(\Delta t)^3}{2} & \frac{(\Delta t)^2}{2} \\ \frac{(\Delta t)^3}{2} & \frac{(\Delta t)^2}{2} & \Delta t \end{bmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

where \dot{x} and \ddot{x} are first and second time derivative, respectively, Δt is the discretisation step of the process and observations (constant for our data) and β is a scalar hyper-parameter (related to the noise) that can describe the uncertainty of the filter in actual application, which can be used for tuning of the SMCKF for a different machine.

Observation matrices corresponding to models 1, 2, 3 are defined as follows:

$$H_t^1 = H_t^2 = H_t^3 = [1, 0, 0]. \quad (26)$$

The measurement noise term is a scalar in our application, and its variance M_t is fixed and independent of s_t for each case but dependent on the particular case (simulation, real data analysis) we use different values, as described in the following sections. The matrix containing the transition probabilities z_{ij} is fixed and defined as follows (note that there is no possibility of transition to the previous state):

$$Z = \begin{bmatrix} 0.998 & 0.001 & 0.001 \\ \sim 0 & 0.999 & 0.001 \\ \sim 0 & \sim 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (27)$$

The vector containing initial probabilities of each stage or MCKF (i.e π_0^1 , π_0^2 and π_0^3) is set as

$$\pi_0 = [0.9, 0.05, 0.05]. \quad (28)$$

The initial estimate state of the model and its covariance matrix have the following form, respectively:

$$\tilde{x}_{0|0} = \begin{bmatrix} y_0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{P}_{0|0} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (29)$$

3. Simulation

In this section, at first, the long-term data is generated based on assumptions presented in Section 2.1. Then the proposed methodology is employed to segment data into three regimes for two different cases: 1) in the presence of Gaussian noise, 2) in the presence of Student's t-distributed noise.

3.1. Generating Signal

According to the model structure discussed in section 2.1, we propose the following model for generating HI, which will be utilized in the simulation:

$$HI(t) = R(t) + D(t), \quad (30)$$

where $R(t)$ and $D(t)$ are random and deterministic parts, respectively. Both mentioned components are composed of three parts, indicated as stage 1, stage 2, and stage 3, which correspond to healthy stage, degradation stage and critical stage, and specify the behavior of the degradation process. Let us consider that we have a sample series $HI(1), \dots, HI(N)$. The changing points between these stages are denoted with τ_1 and τ_2 , which refer to the changing point between the healthy stage to the degradation stage and degradation to the critical stage, respectively. Therefore, the series $HI(1), \dots, HI(\tau_1)$ corresponds to stage 1, the series $HI(\tau_1 + 1), \dots, HI(\tau_2)$ refers to stage 2 and the series $HI(\tau_2 + 1), \dots, HI(N)$ corresponds to stage 3. The same terminology we use for the sequences $R(t)$ and the function $D(t)$.

In the simulation study presented in the next section, we assume two distributions for the random component, namely Gaussian and Student's t-distributed. The aim of using both Gaussian and Student's t-distribution (being an example of a heavy-tailed distribution) in the simulation is to provide a comparison between them for condition monitoring application, as non-Gaussian behavior is widely present in real scenarios. It should be noted that the Student's t-distribution was chosen because it is both heavy-tailed (unlike Gaussian distribution) and at the same time has finite variance (for the considered range of number of degrees of freedom), making it easier to fit than some other theoretically well-established distributions. Also, in our previous paper, we showed that this distribution could describe a random part properly [53]. The random component corresponding to $R(t)$ is constructed in the following way:

$$R(t) = SC(t)\hat{R}(t), \quad (31)$$

where the function $SC(t)$ and $\hat{R}(t)$ denote the time-changing scale and a series of independent identically distributed random variables, respectively, for the case with the Gaussian distribution, for every t we assume $\hat{R}(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ and for the Student's t-distribution case $\hat{R}(t) \sim t(\nu)$ where ν is the number of degrees of freedom. For simplicity, we consider that the distribution in each stage is the same; however, as was mentioned in Section 2.1, in practice, it may be different for different stages. As it was discussed, the random component inherent in the degradation process may be characterized differently for each stage; namely, for simulation we assume that in stage 1, the scale grows linearly, from σ_1 to σ_2 (where both values are relatively close to each other). In stage 2 it also grows linearly, from σ_2 to σ_3 , and ultimately, in stage 3 it increases exponentially, from σ_3 to σ_4 . Therefore, the function $SC(t)$ is represented as follows

$$SC(t) = \begin{cases} a_1 t + b_1 & 0 < t \leq \tau_1, \\ a_2 t + b_2 & \tau_1 < t \leq \tau_2, \\ a_3 \exp(b_3 t) & \tau_2 < t \leq N, \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

where constants $a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, a_3, b_3$ are derived in such a way that $SC(1) = \sigma_1, SC(\tau_1) = \sigma_2, SC(\tau_2) = \sigma_3$ and $SC(N) = \sigma_4$.

Furthermore, the behavior of the deterministic component $D(t)$ in Eq. (30) is described with different trends for different stages. Let us remember that in stage 1, it is at the fixed constant level, indicated here as c_1 . Then, in stage 2 we consider linear growth and in stage the trend is described with exponential function with the same transition parameters as for the corresponding stages of the scale function $SC(t)$. Moreover, we assume the function $D(t)$ has no discontinuities in the stage changing points τ_1 and τ_2 . Under this consideration, the deterministic term of the signal has the form:

$$D(t) = \begin{cases} c_1 & 0 < t \leq \tau_1, \\ a_2 t + c_2 & \tau_1 < t \leq \tau_2, \\ a_3 \exp(b_3 t) + c_3 & \tau_2 < t \leq N, \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

where c_2 and c_3 are derived in such a way that $D(t)$ is continuous function. In panel (a) in Fig. 6 we present the deterministic component $D(t)$ and exemplary trajectories of the random component $R(t)$ for the following values of the parameters: $\tau_1 = 1000$, $\tau_2 = 1600$, $N = 1700$, $\sigma_1 = 1$, $\sigma_2 = 2$, $\sigma_3 = 7$, $\sigma_4 = 25$ and $c_1 = 10$. Here we assume $\nu = 3$. As can be seen, for the Gaussian distributed signal, we do not observe the outlying observations see panel (b) in Fig. 6, while for the non-Gaussian heavy-tailed case, large impulses occur in the data, see panel (c) in Fig. 6. The smaller the ν , the higher impulses may occur in the signal.

Figure 6: Simulated model: (a) deterministic part plus changing points, (b) Gaussian noise, (c) non-Gaussian noise, (d) HI in the presence of Gaussian noise, (e) HI in the presence of non-Gaussian noise.

As it was discussed, in the actual CM data, non-Gaussian behavior is inherent, but sometimes, it is enough to consider a Gaussian model, which is easier to analyse. Therefore both cases were taken into account. To justify why the Student's t-distribution was chosen as a distribution for modeling of the non-Gaussian case, we highlight that besides having heavy tails (rare events like impulses in the signal are not neglected in the modelling), it has finite variance (for number of degrees of freedom $\nu > 2$), and as its limit case, it has the Gaussian distribution (when ν comes to infinity). This enables a more straightforward estimation than other distributions popular with theoretical research (for instance, stable distribution) [53].

3.2. Gaussian noise

In this subsection, the proposed methodology is applied to data generated by the suggested model, assuming that the noise term has Gaussian distribution $\hat{R}(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1)$. The segmentation results for simulated data are presented together for all of the selected methods. Due to the simulation procedure at Time=1000, the healthy stage is switching to the degradation stage (CP1), and Time=1600 is the border point between the degradation stage and the critical stage (CP2).

In Fig. 7 the results of the implementation of the proposed method, plus classic SKF, are presented. Panel (a) shows the HI and actual changing point (CP). Panels (b) and (c) illustrate the probability of each stage (i.e. $\pi_t^1, \pi_t^2, \pi_t^3$) performed by SKF and SMCKF, respectively. Green, yellow, and red lines refer to the healthy, degradation, and critical stages. As we can see on these panels, from Time =0 to 1000, probability of the model being in the healthy stage is the highest among all three stages; the probability of the healthy stage is reduced close to Time=1000 while the probability of the degradation stage increases

around this time. Behind Time=1000, the degradation stage remains with the highest probability stage till Time= 1600. After Time=1600, the critical stage has the highest probability. As we expected, in the presence of Gaussian noise both methods give approximately the same results. Moreover, on panels (d) and (e), the most probable state during the degradation process, plus the changing points between stages, are shown.

Figure 7: Detection of the stages in the presence of Gaussian noise, (a) HI, (b) probability of stages performed by SKF, (c) probability of stages performed by SMCKF, (d) most probable stages based on the implementation of SKF, (e) most probable stages based on the implementation of SMCKF.

3.3. Non-Gaussian noise

In this part, the proposed methodology is applied to data generated by the offered model, considering that the noise term has Student's t-distribution with a number of degrees of freedom $\nu = 3$. According to the simulation procedure, CP1 and CP2 are equal to Time=1000 and Time=1600, respectively.

Fig. 8 shows the result of the proposed methods when noise is non-Gaussian. The estimated probability of each state using SKF and MCKF during the degradation process is presented in panels (b) and (c), respectively. On panel (b), we can see the probability of the healthy stage (the green line) is starting to reduce from Time=300; after a few fluctuations with the degradation stage (the yellow line), somewhere around Time=880, the degradation stage will be the most probable stage which remains on this situation until Time=1446. Behind this time, the critic stage has bigger probability than the other two, but as we can see on panel (b) in Fig. 8, the SKF has diverged after Time=1500. Panel (c) presented the result of SMCKF. Also, the most probable stage during the degradation process and changing points extracted by employing SKF and SMCKF are shown in panels (d) and (e). By comparing these two last panels, as expected, the SMCKF result is closer to the actual changing points. SKF on the other hand has been significantly affected by non-Gaussian noise and, at the end, diverges, which makes the results from SKF not acceptable.

Figure 8: Detection of the stages in the presence of non-Gaussian noise, (a) HI, (b) probability of stages by SKF, (c) probability of stages by SMCKF, (d) most probable stages based on the implementation of SKF, (e) most probable stages based on the implementation of SMCKF.

The proposed procedure was repeated for 100 simulations from the same model for a different level of non-Gaussian noise (different number of degrees of freedom ν), and the sensitivity and specificity values were calculated for each simulation then their mean were calculated and presented in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, respectively. Also, it should be noted that the kernel size value is selected $\sigma = 0.391$ for all simulations.

The sensitivity results are presented in Fig. 9. As can be seen in panel (a), the SKF method has a better result than the proposed method for the healthy stage; however, the difference is very small, and the value for both methods is close to one for various ranges of ν . The sensitivity results for the degradation stage is presented on panel (b); as it can be seen, the results for SMCKF is more or less stable for different value of ν , and the value of sensitivity is more than 0.9, while the sensitivity of the SKF is very low for lower value of ν . Furthermore, as can be seen in panel (b), the sensitivity of the SKF is increased by increasing the value of ν , which shows the influence of the non-Gaussianity level on the performance of SKF. Also, the situation for the last stage (critical stage) is the same as the degradation stage, see panel (c). The sensitivity of the SMCKF is higher (approximately close to one) and more stable than SKF for the last stage. Furthermore, it should be noted that due to the results presented in Fig. 9, particularly in the two last panels, the SMCKF has better performance than SKF, even when the noise is entirely close to the Gaussian (for $\nu = 100$).

Figure 9: Sensitivity analysis, (a) health stage, (b) degradation stage, (c) critical stage.

The specificity results are presented in Fig. 10. As seen in panels (a) and panel (b), the SMCKF has a higher (approximately close to one) and more stable specificity value than SKF. Also, in both mentioned panels, the specificity of the SKF is very low for smaller ν . The same as in the case of sensitivity, the influence of the non-Gaussianity level on the performance of SKF is visible. Also, in the last stage (critical stage), the SKF has a better performance than SMCKF; however, the difference is very small, and both methods have specificity close to 1 for all ν values.

Figure 10: Specificity analysis, (a) health stage, (b) degradation stage, (c) critical stage.

4. Real data analysis

This section evaluates the proposed methodology for available real data sets. These data are typically employed as benchmark data sets for different papers and competitions and have specific behavior corresponding to noise properties and deterministic trends. In the following, essential information about objects, experiments, and data will be recalled, and appropriate references are provided.

4.1. FEMTO data set

The FEMTO data set comprises 17 historical runs to failure of bearing degradation using the PRONOSTIA platform see Fig. 11. Franche-Comté Electronics Mechanics Thermal Science and Optics–Sciences and Technologies institute recorded and published this data set as PHM challenge 2012. The frequency resolution of the data set is 25600 Hz. But, the length of the signal is 0.1 second, so it is not enough to apply most conventional frequency analyses and spectrograms. More information about this data set can be found in [66]. This data set has been employed in many publications for HI construction [67–74], segmentation of degradation process [75–79], and RUL prediction [80–85].

Figure 11: PRONOSTIA platform [66].

In this paper, the bearing 1 – 1 is selected as a case study from the FEMTO data set, which is composed of a few historical vibration data. Each of the mentioned sets acquired 0.1 seconds vibration signal with a 25.6 kHz sampling rate; see panel (a) in Fig. 12. This process is repeated every 10 seconds. Also, in this paper, the RMS of each vibration set is used as HI; see panel (b) in Fig. 12.

Figure 12: FEMTO data set, (a) raw bearing run-to-failure vibration signals, (b) HI. (RMS of the raw signal)

4.2. Wind turbine data set

This data set is collected from a wind turbine see Fig. 13. The sensor has been mounted on a high-speed bearing shaft of the 2.2 MW power wind turbine. This data set is acquired for more than 50 days using two different ways. In the first approach, raw vibration signal is acquired for 6 seconds with 100k sampling frequency per day for +50 days, see panel (a) of Fig. 14. For the second version, the bearing inner race energy is calculated every 10 min for +50 days see panel (b) of Fig. 14. Then for more information about the methodology for calculating inner race energy, see [86]. At the end, the inner race-bearing fault occurred, which was proved by inspection. The bearing type used during the test is 32222 – J2- SKF. It should be mentioned that this data set has been used for prognosis by several papers, see, e.g., [86–89].

Figure 13: Wind turbine data set platform (top) and photo of the damage.

For the application of the proposed approach to the wind turbine data set, inner race energy is selected as a health index. As can be seen in panel (b) of Fig. 14 this data set includes numerous outliers. Thus, we consider it as a trend with non-Gaussian noise [53]. In addition, a few fluctuations have appeared on HI that may correspond to the variation of the load or some phenomena like self-healing. This specific behavior in real cases significantly challenges the diagnostic and prediction of RUL.

Figure 14: Wind turbine data set, (a) raw bearing run-to-failure vibration signals, (b) HI (inner race energy of the raw signal).

4.3. FEMTO diagnostics result

In Fig. 15 the SMCKF, and SKF results on FEMTO data set is demonstrated. Panels (b) and (c) are shown the probability of the stages (i.e. $\pi_t^1, \pi_t^2, \pi_t^3$) during the degradation process based on SKF and SMCKF, respectively. Also, the most probable stage detected and changing points between stages by SKF and SMCKF are illustrated in panels (d) and (e), respectively. By comparing the results of SKF and SMCKF in the two last panels, it can be seen that the results more or less are same even though on the panel (d) that SKF, we can see fluctuation around Time=1300. Also, in both methods, the critical stage is detected on Time=2411, which seems to be identified earlier than the actual changing point.

Figure 15: Segmentation of the FEMTO data set, (a) HI, (b) probability of stage by SKF, (c) probability of stage by SMCKF, (d) most probable stages based on the implementation of SKF, (e) most probable stages based on the implementation of SMCKF.

4.4. Wind turbine diagnostics result

In Fig. 16, the SMCKF and SKF results from the wind turbine data set are demonstrated. Panels (b) and (c) show the probability of stages during the degradation process based on SKF and SMCKF, respectively. Also, the most probable stage detected and changing points between stages by SKF and SMCKF are illustrated in panels (d) and (e), respectively. By comparing the results of SKF and SMCKF in the two last panels, it can be seen that both methods detected 18-Mar as the first changing point while the second changing point is identified on 9-Apr by using SKF, and this point is observed on 21-Apr by employing SMCKF.

Figure 16: Segmentation of the Wind turbine data set, (a) HI, (b) probability of stage by SKF, (c) probability of stage by SMCKF, (d) most probable stages based on the implementation of SKF, (e) most probable stages based on the implementation of SMCKF.

As discussed, this data set has two versions; another version is collected and composed of a raw vibration signal recorded for six seconds daily with a 100k sampling rate, see panel (a) in Fig. 17. So it means it has an excellent potential to apply various methods of frequency analysis to do condition monitoring. The envelope analysis is applied for each vibration set, and the results are sequentially plotted in panel (b) of Fig. 17. As shown in panel (b) in Fig. 17 after 18 March, harmonic frequency appeared, which means the bearing went to the degradation stage. Also, after 22 April, the amplitude of harmonic frequency is dramatically increased, which can be considered CP2. By comparing the SMCKF and SKF results to the envelope analysis, it can be found that CP1 and CP2, identified by SMCKF (CP1=18 March and CP2 =22 April), has the closest value to the CP1 and CP2 detected by visual check on envelope analysis.

Figure 17: Changing points detection via envelope analysis for Wind turbine, (a) raw bearing run-to-failure vibration signals, (b) waterfall plot of envelope spectrum calculated for available raw vibration data.

Table 2 demonstrates the computational cost of both methods for real data sets. The proposed method is implemented with Matlab 2021b, and the hardware property of the system for this implementation are as follows: Processor: Intel (R) Core (TM) i7-10750H CPU @ 2.60GHz 2.59 GHz and Ram: 32.0 GB. As shown in Table 2, the computational cost of SKF and SMCKF are low. However, the SKF is a faster method than SMCKF.

Table 2: Computational cost

	SKF	SMCKF
FEMTO data set	0.358424 (s)	1.052233 (s)
Wind turbine data set	0.524977 (s)	1.658114 (s)

Furthermore, in this paper, we selected the kernel size σ by using trial and error, which is a drawback of the proposed methodology that, in the future, we will try to deal with this problem.

5. Conclusions

This paper introduces a robust methodology for online diagnostics of long-term condition monitoring data in the presence of non-Gaussian noise. The long-term data describes the degradation process. Several approaches assume a model of such degradation. Therefore, a general look at different degradation processes was carried out. Due to this, it is assumed that degradation can evolve over time. It comprises three stages corresponding to the machine life phases: healthy, degradation, and critical stages, see Fig. 3. In actual applications, it is essential to identify when a machine's condition changes from a healthy stage to a degradation stage (warning) and the degradation stage to a critical stage (alarm). It is the base of additional analyses like prognostics. Furthermore, researchers focus on the last segment. However, they don't mention how they have found the division between stages 2 and 3 and whether this detected point coincides with the true start time of the rapid development of the fault in the machine. Each of these stages is modeled by MCKF, being a robust version of the Kalman filter. The SMCKF is introduced to infer from the current observations of the underlying process by calculating which of the three filters has the biggest probability in each time step. This method can provide more information to the decision-maker by providing probabilistic information about each degradation stage over time. Furthermore, this method works according to the dynamic trend of the degradation process, and the threshold is no longer needed. Also, the proposed method's computational cost is low, which has massive potential to employ it for actual applications. Moreover, it provides a possibility to start the prediction of RUL from the beginning of the critical stage (which has advantages). The biggest drawback of this approach is that the measurement

noise part of the processes has been tuned manually. In the future work, the solution to address it will be investigated in detail.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Bibliography

- [1] Y. Lei, N. Li, L. Guo, N. Li, T. Yan, J. Lin, Machinery health prognostics: A systematic review from data acquisition to RUL prediction, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 104 (2018) 799–834.
- [2] X.-S. Si, W. Wang, C.-H. Hu, D.-H. Zhou, Remaining useful life estimation—a review on the statistical data driven approaches, *European Journal of Operational Research* 213 (1) (2011) 1–14.
- [3] Z.-S. Ye, M. Xie, Stochastic modelling and analysis of degradation for highly reliable products, *Applied Stochastic Models in Business and Industry* 31 (1) (2015) 16–32.
- [4] D. Kucharczyk, A. Wylomańska, J. Obuchowski, R. Zimroz, M. Madziarz, Stochastic modelling as a tool for seismic signals segmentation, *Shock and Vibration* 2016 (2016).
- [5] K. Kourou, T. P. Exarchos, K. P. Exarchos, M. V. Karamouzis, D. I. Fotiadis, Machine learning applications in cancer prognosis and prediction, *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal* 13 (2015) 8–17.
- [6] K. Thomsen, L. Iversen, T. L. Titlestad, O. Winther, Systematic review of machine learning for diagnosis and prognosis in dermatology, *Journal of Dermatological Treatment* 31 (5) (2020) 496–510.
- [7] A. Diez-Oliván, J. Del Ser, D. Galar, B. Sierra, Data fusion and machine learning for industrial prognosis: trends and perspectives towards industry 4.0, *Information Fusion* 50 (2019) 92–111.
- [8] A. Heng, S. Zhang, A. C. Tan, J. Mathew, Rotating machinery prognostics: State of the art, challenges and opportunities, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 23 (3) (2009) 724–739.
- [9] M. S. Kan, A. C. Tan, J. Mathew, A review on prognostic techniques for non-stationary and non-linear rotating systems, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 62 (2015) 1–20.
- [10] L. Liao, F. Köttig, Review of hybrid prognostics approaches for remaining useful life prediction of engineered systems, and an application to battery life prediction, *IEEE Transactions on Reliability* 63 (1) (2014) 191–207.
- [11] Z. Zhao, J. Wu, T. Li, C. Sun, R. Yan, X. Chen, Challenges and opportunities of ai-enabled monitoring, diagnosis & prognosis: A review, *Chinese Journal of Mechanical Engineering* 34 (1) (2021) 1–29.
- [12] F. Moosavi, H. Shiri, J. Wodecki, A. Wylomańska, R. Zimroz, Application of machine learning tools for long-term diagnostic feature data segmentation, *Applied Sciences* 12 (13) (2022) 6766.
- [13] P. Tamilselvan, Y. Wang, P. Wang, Deep belief network based state classification for structural health diagnosis, in: 2012 IEEE Aerospace Conference, IEEE, 2012, pp. 1–11.
- [14] J. Liu, F. Lei, C. Pan, D. Hu, H. Zuo, Prediction of remaining useful life of multi-stage aero-engine based on clustering and lstm fusion, *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 214 (2021) 107807.
- [15] J. Singh, A. Darpe, S. P. Singh, Bearing remaining useful life estimation using an adaptive data-driven model based on health state change point identification and k-means clustering, *Measurement Science and Technology* 31 (8) (2020) 085601.
- [16] W. Mao, J. He, B. Sun, L. Wang, Prediction of bearings remaining useful life across working conditions based on transfer learning and time series clustering, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 135285–135303.
- [17] S. Sharanya, R. Venkataraman, G. Murali, Estimation of remaining useful life of bearings using reduced affinity propagated clustering, *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology* 16 (5) (2021) 3737–3756.
- [18] K. Javed, R. Gouriveau, N. Zerhouni, A new multivariate approach for prognostics based on extreme learning machine and fuzzy clustering, *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics* 45 (12) (2015) 2626–2639.
- [19] Z. Chen, M. Wu, R. Zhao, F. Guretno, R. Yan, X. Li, Machine remaining useful life prediction via an attention-based deep learning approach, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 68 (3) (2020) 2521–2531.

- [20] K. Gong, X. Chen, Influence of non-Gaussian wind characteristics on wind turbine extreme response, *Engineering Structures* 59 (2014) 727–744.
- [21] K. R. Gurley, M. A. Tognarelli, A. Kareem, Analysis and simulation tools for wind engineering, *Probabilistic Engineering Mechanics* 12 (1) (1997) 9–31.
- [22] A. Kareem, J. Zhao, Analysis of non-Gaussian surge response of tension leg platforms under wind loads, *Journal of Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering* 116 (3) (1994) 137–144.
- [23] J. Hebda-Sobkowicz, R. Zimroz, A. Wylomańska, J. Antoni, Infogram performance analysis and its enhancement for bearings diagnostics in presence of non-Gaussian noise, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 170 (2022) 108764.
- [24] J. Nowicki, J. Hebda-Sobkowicz, R. Zimroz, A. Wylomańska, Dependency measures for the diagnosis of local faults in application to the heavy-tailed vibration signal, *Applied Acoustics* 178 (2021) 107974.
- [25] T. Kobayashi, D. L. Simon, Application of a bank of Kalman filters for aircraft engine fault diagnostics, in: *Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, Vol. 36843, 2003, pp. 461–470.
- [26] C. Sadhukhan, S. K. Mitra, M. K. Naskar, M. Sharifpur, Fault diagnosis of a nonlinear hybrid system using adaptive unscented Kalman filter bank, *Engineering with Computers* 38 (3) (2022) 2717–2728.
- [27] Q. Yu, L. Dai, R. Xiong, Z. Chen, X. Zhang, W. Shen, Current sensor fault diagnosis method based on an improved equivalent circuit battery model, *Applied Energy* 310 (2022) 118588.
- [28] S. Cho, M. Choi, Z. Gao, T. Moan, Fault detection and diagnosis of a blade pitch system in a floating wind turbine based on Kalman filters and artificial neural networks, *Renewable Energy* 169 (2021) 1–13.
- [29] Y. Li, K. Feng, X. Liang, M. J. Zuo, A fault diagnosis method for planetary gearboxes under non-stationary working conditions using improved Vold-Kalman filter and multi-scale sample entropy, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 439 (2019) 271–286.
- [30] L. Keizers, R. Loendersloot, T. Tinga, Unscented Kalman filtering for prognostics under varying operational and environmental conditions, *International Journal of Prognostics and Health Management* 12 (2) (2021).
- [31] M. Baptista, E. M. Henriques, I. P. de Medeiros, J. P. Malere, C. L. Nascimento Jr, H. Prendinger, Remaining useful life estimation in aeronautics: combining data-driven and Kalman filtering, *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 184 (2019) 228–239.
- [32] J. Weddington, G. Niu, R. Chen, W. Yan, B. Zhang, Lithium-ion battery diagnostics and prognostics enhanced with Dempster-Shafer decision fusion, *Neurocomputing* 458 (2021) 440–453.
- [33] C. K. R. Lim, D. Mba, Switching Kalman filter for failure prognostic, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 52 (2015) 426–435.
- [34] H. W. Sorenson, D. L. Alspach, Recursive Bayesian estimation using Gaussian sums, *Automatica* 7 (4) (1971) 465–479.
- [35] A. Harvey, A. Luati, Filtering with heavy tails, *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 109 (507) (2014) 1112–1122.
- [36] D. Magill, Optimal adaptive estimation of sampled stochastic processes, *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* 10 (4) (1965) 434–439.
- [37] I. Bilik, J. Tabrikian, MMSE-based filtering in presence of non-Gaussian system and measurement noise, *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems* 46 (3) (2010) 1153–1170.
- [38] D. Alspach, H. Sorenson, Nonlinear Bayesian estimation using Gaussian sum approximations, *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* 17 (4) (1972) 439–448.
- [39] J. H. Kotecha, P. M. Djuric, Gaussian sum particle filtering, *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing* 51 (10) (2003) 2602–2612.
- [40] A. Doucet, N. De Freitas, N. J. Gordon, et al., *Sequential Monte Carlo methods in practice*, Vol. 1, Springer, 2001.
- [41] P. M. Djuric, J. H. Kotecha, J. Zhang, Y. Huang, T. Ghirmai, M. F. Bugallo, J. Miguez, Particle filtering, *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* 20 (5) (2003) 19–38.
- [42] S. J. Julier, J. K. Uhlmann, Unscented filtering and nonlinear estimation, *Proceedings of the IEEE* 92 (3) (2004) 401–422.
- [43] R. Izanloo, S. A. Fakoorian, H. S. Yazdi, D. Simon, Kalman filtering based on the maximum correntropy criterion in the presence of non-Gaussian noise, in: *2016 Annual Conference on Information Science and Systems (CISS)*, IEEE, 2016, pp. 500–505.
- [44] B. Chen, X. Liu, H. Zhao, J. C. Principe, Maximum correntropy Kalman filter, *Automatica* 76 (2017) 70–77.
- [45] G. Wang, R. Xue, J. Wang, A distributed maximum correntropy Kalman filter, *Signal Processing* 160 (2019) 247–251.
- [46] G. Wang, Y. Zhang, X. Wang, Iterated maximum correntropy unscented Kalman filters for non-Gaussian systems, *Signal Processing* 163 (2019) 87–94.
- [47] Y. Bar-Shalom, X. R. Li, T. Kirubarajan, *Estimation with applications to tracking and navigation: theory algorithms and software*, John Wiley & Sons, 2004.
- [48] Y. P. Lim, S.-F. Cheng, Knowledge-driven autonomous commodity trading advisor, in: *2012 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Conferences on Web Intelligence and Intelligent Agent Technology*, Vol. 2, IEEE, 2012, pp. 119–125.
- [49] V. Manfredi, S. Mahadevan, J. Kurose, Switching Kalman filters for prediction and tracking in an adaptive meteorological sensing network, in: *2005 Second Annual IEEE Communications Society Conference on Sensor and Ad Hoc Communications and Networks*, 2005. *IEEE SECON 2005.*, Citeseer, 2005, pp. 197–206.
- [50] Y. Zhang, J. Jiang, Integrated active fault-tolerant control using IMM approach, *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems* 37 (4) (2001) 1221–1235.
- [51] X. Wang, V. L. Syrmos, Interacting multiple particle filters for fault diagnosis of non-linear stochastic systems, in: *2008 American Control Conference*, IEEE, 2008, pp. 4274–4279.
- [52] L. C. K. Reuben, D. Mba, Diagnostics and prognostics using switching Kalman filters, *Structural Health Monitoring* 13 (3) (2014) 296–306.
- [53] W. Zulawinski, K. Maraj-Zygmunt, H. Shiri, A. Wylomska, R. Zimroz, Framework for stochastic modelling of long-term

- non-homogeneous data with non-Gaussian characteristics for machine condition prognosis, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 184 (2023) 109677.
- [54] D. Zhang, An adaptive procedure for tool life prediction in face milling, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part J: Journal of Engineering Tribology* 225 (11) (2011) 1130–1136.
- [55] S. Liu, J. Wang, H. Liu, Q. Liu, J. Tang, Z. Li, Battery degradation model and multiple-indicators based lifetime estimator for energy storage system design and operation: Experimental analyses of cycling-induced aging, *Electrochimica Acta* 384 (2021) 138294.
- [56] L. Zhang, Z. Mu, C. Sun, Remaining useful life prediction for lithium-ion batteries based on exponential model and particle filter, *IEEE Access* 6 (2018) 17729–17740.
- [57] P. Ma, S. Wang, L. Zhao, M. Pecht, X. Su, Z. Ye, An improved exponential model for predicting the remaining useful life of lithium-ion batteries, in: 2015 IEEE Conference on Prognostics and Health Management (PHM), IEEE, 2015, pp. 1–6.
- [58] C. Pan, Y. Chen, L. Wang, Z. He, Lithium-ion battery remaining useful life prediction based on exponential smoothing and particle filter, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci* 14 (9) (2019) 9537–9551.
- [59] C. Lim, D. Mba, Switching Kalman filter for failure prognostic, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 52-53 (1) (2015) 426 – 435.
- [60] L. Cui, X. Wang, H. Wang, J. Ma, Research on remaining useful life prediction of rolling element bearings based on time-varying Kalman filter, *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 69 (6) (2019) 2858–2867.
- [61] R. I. Stephens, A. Fatemi, R. R. Stephens, H. O. Fuchs, *Metal fatigue in engineering*, John Wiley & Sons, 2000.
- [62] [Linear elastic fracture mechanics \(lefm\): Part two](https://www.totalmateria.com/page.aspx?ID=CheckArticle&LN=EN&site=KTS&NM=299) (Dec 2010).
URL <https://www.totalmateria.com/page.aspx?ID=CheckArticle&LN=EN&site=KTS&NM=299>
- [63] L. Reuben, D. Mba, Diagnostics and prognostics using switching Kalman filters, *Structural Health Monitoring* 13 (3) (2014) 296 – 306.
- [64] M. Kevin, Learning switching Kalman filter models, 98-10, Compaq Cambridge Research Lab Tech Report (1998).
- [65] N. A. Mustafa, et al., Design of smart wearable system for sudden infant death syndrome monitoring, Ph.D. thesis, Sudan University of Science and Technology (2021).
- [66] P. Nectoux, R. Gouriveau, K. Medjaher, E. Ramasso, B. Chebel-Morello, N. Zerhouni, C. Varnier, Pronostia: An experimental platform for bearings accelerated degradation tests., in: IEEE International Conference on Prognostics and Health Management, PHM'12., IEEE Catalog Number: CPF12PHM-CDR, 2012, pp. 1–8.
- [67] A. Mosallam, K. Medjaher, N. Zerhouni, Time series trending for condition assessment and prognostics, *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management* (2014).
- [68] T. H. Loutas, D. Roulias, G. Georgoulas, Remaining useful life estimation in rolling bearings utilizing data-driven probabilistic e-support vectors regression, *IEEE Transactions on Reliability* 62 (4) (2013) 821–832.
- [69] K. Javed, R. Gouriveau, N. Zerhouni, P. Nectoux, Enabling health monitoring approach based on vibration data for accurate prognostics, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 62 (1) (2014) 647–656.
- [70] R. K. Singleton, E. G. Strangas, S. Aviyente, Extended Kalman filtering for remaining-useful-life estimation of bearings, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* 62 (3) (2014) 1781–1790.
- [71] B. Zhang, L. Zhang, J. Xu, Degradation feature selection for remaining useful life prediction of rolling element bearings, *Quality and Reliability Engineering International* 32 (2) (2016) 547–554.
- [72] S. Hong, Z. Zhou, E. Zio, W. Wang, An adaptive method for health trend prediction of rotating bearings, *Digital Signal Processing* 35 (2014) 117–123.
- [73] Y. Lei, N. Li, S. Gontarz, J. Lin, S. Radkowski, J. Dybala, A model-based method for remaining useful life prediction of machinery, *IEEE Transactions on Reliability* 65 (3) (2016) 1314–1326.
- [74] Y. Nie, J. Wan, Estimation of remaining useful life of bearings using sparse representation method, in: 2015 Prognostics and System Health Management Conference (PHM), IEEE, 2015, pp. 1–6.
- [75] Z. Liu, M. J. Zuo, Y. Qin, Remaining useful life prediction of rolling element bearings based on health state assessment, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part C: Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science* 230 (2) (2016) 314–330.
- [76] J. K. Kimotho, C. Sondermann-Wölke, T. Meyer, W. Sextro, Machinery prognostic method based on multi-class support vector machines and hybrid differential evolution–particle swarm optimization, *Chemical Engineering Transactions* 33 (2013).
- [77] D. Zurita, J. A. Carino, M. Delgado, J. A. Ortega, Distributed neuro-fuzzy feature forecasting approach for condition monitoring, in: Proceedings of the 2014 IEEE Emerging Technology and Factory Automation (ETFA), IEEE, 2014, pp. 1–8.
- [78] L. Guo, H. Gao, H. Huang, X. He, S. Li, Multifeatures fusion and nonlinear dimension reduction for intelligent bearing condition monitoring, *Shock and Vibration* 2016 (2016).
- [79] X. Jin, Y. Sun, Z. Que, Y. Wang, T. W. Chow, Anomaly detection and fault prognosis for bearings, *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 65 (9) (2016) 2046–2054.
- [80] H. Li, Y. Wang, Rolling bearing reliability estimation based on logistic regression model, in: 2013 International Conference on Quality, Reliability, Risk, Maintenance, and Safety Engineering (QR2MSE), IEEE, 2013, pp. 1730–1733.
- [81] Z. Huang, Z. Xu, X. Ke, W. Wang, Y. Sun, Remaining useful life prediction for an adaptive skew-Wiener process model, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 87 (2017) 294–306.
- [82] Y. Wang, Y. Peng, Y. Zi, X. Jin, K.-L. Tsui, A two-stage data-driven-based prognostic approach for bearing degradation problem, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 12 (3) (2016) 924–932.
- [83] Y. Pan, M. J. Er, X. Li, H. Yu, R. Gouriveau, Machine health condition prediction via online dynamic fuzzy neural networks, *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 35 (2014) 105–113.

- [84] L. Wang, L. Zhang, X.-z. Wang, Reliability estimation and remaining useful lifetime prediction for bearing based on proportional hazard model, *Journal of Central South University* 22 (12) (2015) 4625–4633.
- [85] L. Xiao, X. Chen, X. Zhang, M. Liu, A novel approach for bearing remaining useful life estimation under neither failure nor suspension histories condition, *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* 28 (8) (2017) 1893–1914.
- [86] E. Bechhoefer, R. Schlanbusch, Generalized prognostics algorithm using Kalman smoother, *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 48 (21) (2015) 97–104.
- [87] L. Saidi, J. B. Ali, E. Bechhoefer, M. Benbouzid, Wind turbine high-speed shaft bearings health prognosis through a spectral kurtosis-derived indices and svr, *Applied Acoustics* 120 (2017) 1–8.
- [88] L. Saidi, E. Bechhoefer, J. B. Ali, M. Benbouzid, Wind turbine high-speed shaft bearing degradation analysis for run-to-failure testing using spectral kurtosis, in: *2015 16th International Conference on Sciences and Techniques of Automatic Control and Computer Engineering (STA)*, IEEE, 2015, pp. 267–272.
- [89] J. B. Ali, L. Saidi, S. Harrath, E. Bechhoefer, M. Benbouzid, Online automatic diagnosis of wind turbine bearings progressive degradations under real experimental conditions based on unsupervised machine learning, *Applied Acoustics* 132 (2018) 167–181.